

THYROID CYCLES - CAUSES, SYMPTOMS, TREATMENT AND PREVENTION

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Abstract. *Thyroid cyst is a disease characterized by the appearance of fluid-filled nodules. Iodine deficiency is the most common non-communicable disease in humans. This article details all the useful tips you need to maintain a healthy lifestyle!*

Keywords: *Symptoms of Thyroid Cyst, Causes, Diagnosis, Treatment of Thyroid Cyst, Complications, Prevention.*

ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЕ ЩИТОВИДНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ - ПРИЧИНЫ, СИМПТОМЫ, ЛЕЧЕНИЕ И ПРОФИЛАКТИКА

Аннотация. *Киста щитовидной железы – заболевание, характеризующееся появлением заполненных жидкостью узелков. Дефицит йода является наиболее распространенным неинфекционным заболеванием человека. В этой статье подробно описаны все полезные советы, необходимые для поддержания здорового образа жизни!*

Ключевые слова: *симптомы кисты щитовидной железы, причины, диагностика, лечение кисты щитовидной железы, осложнения, профилактика.*

INTRODUCTION

Thyroid cyst is a disease characterized by the appearance of fluid-filled nodules. To diagnose them, doctors first resort to external examination and palpation. The cysts look like dense watery nodules.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Iodine deficiency is one of the most common non-communicable diseases in humans. In general, 2 billion people (WHO) live in the regions of the world where there is an iodine deficiency, 600 million of them have an enlarged thyroid gland, 40 million have a severe mental retardation caused by iodine deficiency.

Hypothyroidism is a clinical syndrome caused by a persistent or long-term deficiency of thyroid hormones in the body or a decrease in their biological effectiveness at the tissue level. Manifest primary hypothyroidism in the population occurs in 0.2-1% of cases, subclinical primary hypothyroidism - in 7-10% of women and in 2-3% of men. Within a year, 5% of subclinical hypothyroidism manifests itself.

RESULTS

Symptoms of thyroid cycles

Regardless of which part of the gland is located, the symptoms are more characteristic in the late stages of disease development. The most noticeable of these is the sensation of a foreign body in the throat. Such nodules can also be detected by simple palpation by hand.

- Over time, in addition to the nodes, the following symptoms begin to appear:
- Difficulty breathing: the cyst puts pressure on the throat, thereby blocking the trachea;
- Pain in the area of the cyst (may spread to the ears and jaw);
- Discomfort and pain when swallowing;
- In some cases, changes in the timbre of the voice.

Reasons

A cyst in the thyroid gland, or in other words, a nodule in the neck, occurs for the following reasons:

- Frequent stressful situations;
 - Psychoemotional disorder;
 - Prolonged recovery after serious illness;
 - Burn;
 - Hypothermia;
 - Hyperthermia;
 - Hyperactive thyroid function;
- Increased or decreased production of thyroid hormones by the pituitary gland.

In addition, cysts can develop due to the following factors:

- Iodine deficiency;
- Thyroid disease;
- Various poisonings;
- Hormonal background disorder;
- Living in unfavorable environmental conditions;
- Mechanical injuries of the thyroid gland;
- Congenital pathologies of organ development and function;
- Hereditary predisposition.

Often, thyroid cysts are caused by iodine deficiency, as well as follicular dystrophy caused by injuries and mechanical trauma.

Diagnosis

- The diagnosis is made using the following tests:
- Ultrasound examination;
- MRT;
- Biopsy - allows the cells to determine the type of cyst and whether it is bad or good quality;
- Scintigraphy;
- Blood test for thyrotropin;
- Pneumography to detect the presence of metastases in other organs.

Treatment of thyroid cycles

If the cyst or nodules in the neck are caused by iodine deficiency and are diagnosed as of good quality, they can be treated. In addition, it can be ruled out that the cyst can cause serious disorders in the patient's body or lead to an increase in the number of cysts. Once the cyst cavity is emptied, special substances are inserted into it to prevent the cyst from drying out and recurring.

DISCUSSION

Therapy requires a comprehensive approach and includes:

- Drugs that control hormone levels;
- Means that eliminate inflammation and help normalize metabolism;
- Anti-tumor drugs;
- Means that improve blood circulation;

- Antibiotics to prevent bacterial infections.
- Surgery to remove a thyroid cyst is usually done using laser coagulation. In other words, this method is called local hyperthermia. It is recognized as a new method and is now considered one of the most popular.

Laser hyperthermia is created in the area of the cyst, which results in cell division. The operation lasts 5-10 minutes, after which antibodies are added if necessary. Among the advantages of this practice are:

- Painless operation;
- Performed in an outpatient setting;
- Noninvasive process;
- No side effects;
- No scars.

CONCLUSIONS

Complications

If a cyst caused by a hormone production disorder is not treated in time or if the treatment is not done properly, the following complications can occur.

- Elevation of body temperature to 40 ° C;
- Intoxication of the body;
- Proliferation of local lymph node tissue;
- Pain in the area where the cyst formed.

Prevention

To prevent the development of cyst cells and, accordingly, its formation, the prophylactic system is applied in the following way:

1. Regular endocrinological examinations;
2. Elimination of any pathologies of the thyroid gland;
3. Adequate intake of vitamins, minerals and iodine;
4. Limit UV exposure.

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